

INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING SPEAKING TO THE INTERMEDIATE LEVEL LEARNERS

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Abstract: Speaking plays a crucial role in second language learning and teaching. Despite its importance, for many years, teaching speaking has been undervalued and English language teachers have gone on teaching speaking just as a repetition of drills or memorization of dialogues. However, today's world requires that the goal of teaching speaking should improve students' communicative skills. This study focused on the effects of interactive teaching strategy on the improvement of speaking skills of students learning English as a second language. And it purposes to explore some innovative teaching methods, techniques and activities used for developing speaking fluency and its effects of pupils oral competency.

Keywords: Teaching English as a second language; speech training; speaking skills; interactive teaching strategy

INTRODUCTION

The title of this talk is innovation and creativity in English language teaching, but have not mentioned innovation yet. Partly this is because I hope what I have been telling you is recognizable as somewhat innovative. Partly it is because I do not believe in innovation for innovation's sake. We should use new technology, for example, when it enhances our teaching, not just for the sake of it. With that caveat, we need to be aware of new technologies and use them where they can enhance our teaching.

As far as speaking is concerned, the Internet is not such a valuable resource as it is in teaching writing or listening for example, since the Internet is a visual medium. However, it can be used to gain access to lots of stimulating materials that can be used for speaking purposes. Most importantly of course the Internet is bigger than the biggest library there ever was, so there is a wealth of information and data that we can use in the classroom available to us. This means that project work is much easier than previously. It is possible to give students a presentation topic, have them research and present it in a much shorter time than previously. In terms of creativity, it means that students can access personally important information at the touch of a mouse. It also means, for example, that they can access visually stimulating examples extremely easily.

Speaking is very important because by mastering speaking skill, people can carry out conversations with others, give the ideas and exchange the information with others. In speaking, students should master the elements of speaking, such as vocabularies, pronunciation, grammar, and fluency. While it is a bit of an exaggeration, students clearly feel that classroom-based speaking practice does not prepare them for the real world. As a foreign learner in Republic of Uzbekistan, many students have amount vocabularies and mastering the grammatical structure, but they still have difficulty in speaking.

The mastery of speaking skills in English is a necessary for many second language and foreign language students (Richard, 2008). Therefore, learners often appraise their language learning on how much they think they have developed their skill in spoken language skill. Besides, the proficiency of speaking becomes one of the five skills that should be acquired by every child in this 21 century era which is called as a communication skill (Seamolec on line course 2, 2006). Further, communicating and collaborating and language boundaries become a necessity in diverse and multinational communities. Mutually beneficial relationships are a central undercurrent to accomplishment in Business.

It is important to assess young learners' speaking performance, since speaking is considered as the most rewarding and motivating skill for them. The young learners usually get excited when they are able to express a few things in target language. Therefore, Ioannou-Georgiou and Pavlou (2003) propose the criteria in assessing young learners' speaking performance, namely: pronunciation, intonation and turn taking. Overall, the aim is to achieve oral communication, and the teacher should assess their communicative proficiency in basic functions, such as asking questions or introducing themselves.

METHODS

The teacher should possess some of the qualities while teaching his/her students. The teacher's personality, attitude, dexterously handling teaching materials, knack in answering students' questions, and ability to teach by using techniques instill interest among students. Traditional methods cannot be written off from the classroom at any point of time, but including some of the interesting and innovating teaching methodologies will make students to be focused on the learning process. Cognitive development teachings can be done in the class through tasks

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Two data collection instruments were used in the study. In order to identify the level of speaking skills of students, contents were determined by taking the competency levels identified by the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR, 2018) into consideration. The identified topics were presented to ten experts in the field of English education and to two experts in the field of scale evaluations. The experts were asked to evaluate the topics between 1 (not appropriate) and 5 (very appropriate). The topics that received high scores from the experts were selected and the rest were eliminated. Thus, the validity of speaking topics was established. Due to the possibility of memorization of topics in prepared speeches, topics were presented before the class time and speeches were done without preparation. The topics asked in the pre-tests were not used in the post-tests. Speeches were audio recorded with the consent of students.

The first research question was: "In teaching English as a second language, when the total pretest scores of students in the experiment group in which the interactive teaching strategy is implemented, and students in the control group in which traditional teaching methods are implemented, in the "Speaking Skills Evaluation Scale" are controlled for, there is a significant difference between the post-test scores in the experiment group."

As one of the main purposes of learning a language, to speak and communicate in the target language, is the one that receives feedback the least, it is an aspect that needs to be focused on (Koksal & Dag Pestil, 2014, p. 305). There is limited research in the literature focusing on the improvement of speaking skills in learning English as a second language. Additionally, no study was found that focuses on interactive teaching strategy in learning

English as a second language. Thus, in the current study, the effects of the interactive teaching strategy on the speaking skills of C1 level students learning English as a second language were examined. The findings are evaluated and discussed in alignment with the hypotheses of the research.

Discussion is another type of text that is widely used in mother tongue lessons. The peculiarity of the text of the discussion is that the speaker expresses his reaction to the event being told. He seeks evidence to prove his point and tries to substantiate it. Based on the results of observation and comparison, he rejects a particular opinion and makes his own judgment. Discussion-style texts include good and evil, diligence and greed, honesty and selflessness, righteousness and crookedness, good word and bad word, friendship and enmity, courage and cowardice, manners and obscenity, dignity and worthlessness, patience and impatience. In particular, it is advisable to choose folk proverbs as the subject of the discussion text. For example, "There is no poison in what is said to the face", "The heart is right - the way is right", "Both good words and bad words come out of one mouth", "Sayak a walking stick eats." Of course, it is necessary to set such a goal in front of the text. Because both oral and written texts, as well as texts created by students, help to understand the essence of language phenomena: one prepares the ground for the other. Requiring students to describe the content of a poem in a prose way also has a positive effect on the development of their speech. For example, the study of "Cohesive Sayings" requires a prose narration of the content of Mirtemir's poem "This is the land where I was born." Shortening or expanding the content of a text can also be a great practical help in developing students' oral skills. For example, Alisher Navoi's proverbs, folk sayings and proverbs can be expanded (Shaikhislamov N, 2020).

And, in 2000, Rivers defines "interaction" as "students achieve facility in using a language when their attention is focused on conveying and receiving authentic messages." Rivers states that language teaching is a process of structuring interactive activity. The function of teachers is to create opportunities and the environment of using language effectively and freely.

Creativity, therefore, can be built into your lessons. You just need to get into a mindset where you think of all activities in terms of the three levels of creativity, creativity at the level of new language, creativity at the level of communication, and creativity at the level of new thinking. With every activity that you do, either in the textbook, or ones that you design yourself, work out what level of creativity it is at and then decide whether you need to add other levels to it. Very often you will find creativity at levels 1 and 2 already there, but you will need to add a level 3 activity to bring true creativity. Third order creativity is that where students produce something that is really new for them, not just in terms of language but also in terms of ideas. Since level 3 creativity brings in new thinking, it has the effect of really integrating the new language into the students' psyche. The student is motivated because the new language is not just new language but means something to them personally. For this reason, they will remember and it becomes part of them as a language learner, and, ideally, as a person as well.

Suggestions For Teachers in Teaching Speaking

Here are some suggestions for English language teachers while teaching oral language:

- Provide maximum opportunity to students to speak the target language by providing a rich environment that contains collaborative work, authentic materials and tasks, and shared knowledge.
- Try to involve each student in every speaking activity; for this aim, practice different ways of student participation.
- Reduce teacher speaking time in class while increasing student speaking time. Step back and observe students.
- Indicate positive signs when commenting on a student's response.
- Ask eliciting questions such as "What do you mean? How did you reach that conclusion?" in order to prompt students to speak more.
- Provide written feedback like "Your presentation was really great. It was a good job. I really appreciated your efforts in preparing the materials and efficient use of your voice..."
- Do not correct students' pronunciation mistakes very often while they are speaking. Correction should not distract student from his or her speech.
- Involve speaking activities not only in class but also out of class; contact parents and other people who can help.
- Circulate around classroom to ensure that students are on the right track and see whether they need your help while they work in groups or pairs.
- Provide the vocabulary beforehand that students need in speaking activities.
- Diagnose problems faced by students who have difficulty in expressing themselves in the target language and provide more opportunities to practice the spoken language (Kaiy H, 2006).

CONCLUSION

Krashen and Tarrell (1983) are of the view that 'Language acquisition can take place only when people understand messages in the target language' (p. 19). Through understanding the level of students' learning abilities and capabilities, teachers can focus on providing variety of activities to students to develop their language learning skills. Teacher should create a congenial atmosphere in the classroom in which learners would feel comfortable to be a part of the learning process. Teacher should encourage and welcome ideas from the students without any prejudice. Teacher should give enough private space to students to allow them to think critically and develop their lateral thinking for their better future. Using innovative methodologies in teaching English in the classroom will pave a positive way to students to learn the language meaningfully. Students will understand the significance of learning English as a second language without any fear which will help them to equip with the power of confidence and achievement. Teachers should involve wholeheartedly while designing tasks for students as every student in the classroom should be involved and benefited. Teachers should also concentrate on providing effective curriculum development for students with learning-driven nature instead of examination-driven nature scenario.

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